

Radial Radio Mean Square and Radial Radio Cube Square Difference Labeling of Digraphs

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Abstract: Let D be a strong digraph and let $\vec{d}(u, v)$ denote the distance between any two vertices in D . A radial radio mean square labeling is a one to one mapping f from $V(D)$ to N satisfying the condition $\vec{d}(u, v) + \left\lceil \frac{(f(u))^2 + (f(v))^2}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + rad(D)$ for every $u, v \in V(D)$. The radial radio mean square number of D , $rrmsn(D)$ is the lowest span taken over all radial radio mean labelings of the graph D . A radial radio cube square difference labeling is a one to one mapping f from $V(D)$ to N satisfying the condition $\vec{d}(u, v) + [f(u) + f(v)]^3 - [f(u) - f(v)]^2 \geq 1 + rad(D)$ for every $u, v \in V(D)$. The span of a labeling f is the maximum integer that f maps to a vertex of D . The radial radio cube square difference number of D , $rrcsdn(D)$ is the lowest span taken over all radial radio cube square difference labelings of the graph D . In this paper, we analyze radial radio mean square labeling and radial radio cube square difference labeling for some digraphs.

Keywords: Radial Radio Mean Square, Radial Radio Mean Square Number, Radial Radio Mean Labeling, Radial Radio Cube Square Difference Number, Digraphs.

AMS Subject Classification: 05C78.

I.INTRODUCTION

The graph labeling problem is one of the recent developing area in graph theory. Alex Rosa first introduced this problem in 1967[10]. Radio labeling is motivated by the channel assignment problem introduced by W. K. Hale in 1980[5]. In 2001, Gary Chartrand defined the concept of radio labeling of G [3]. Liu and Zhu first determined the radio number in 2005[6]. Ponraj et al.[8] introduced the notion of radio mean labeling of graphs and investigated radio mean number of some graphs [9]. Arputha Jose T and Giridaran M[1] investigated the radial radio mean number of Mangolian Tent and Diamond graphs.

Here, we extend the definition of radial radio mean labeling for digraphs, we define a new definition for radial radio cube square difference labeling and also we study the radial radio mean square number and radial radio cube square difference number of digraphs.

Radio Labeling is used for X-ray, crystallography, coding theory, network security, network addressing, channel assignment process, social network analysis such as connectivity, scalability, routing, computing ,cell biology etc.,

The following results are used in the subsequent section.

Definition: : Let D be a strong digraph and let $\vec{d}(u, v)$ denote the distance between any two vertices in D . A radial radio mean square labeling is a one to one mapping f from $V(D)$ to N satisfying the condition $\vec{d}(u, v) + \left\lceil \frac{(f(u))^2 + (f(v))^2}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + rad(D)$ for every $u, v \in V(D)$. The span of a labeling f is the maximum integer that f maps to a vertex of D . The radial radio mean square number of D , $rrmsn(D)$ is the lowest span taken over all radial radio mean square labelings of the graph D .

Definition: A radial radio cube square difference labeling is a one to one mapping f from $V(D)$ to N satisfying the condition $\vec{d}(u, v) + |[f(u) + f(v)]^3 - [f(u) - f(v)]^2| \geq 1 + rad(D)$ for every $u, v \in V(D)$. The span of a labeling f is the maximum integer that f maps to a vertex of D . The radial radio cube square difference number of D , $rrcsdn(D)$ is the lowest span taken over all radial radio cube square difference labelings of the graph D .

Definition: Consider a globe. Let u, v be the vertices of degree n . Orient the edges of all but one $u - v$ path of length two in same direction. Orient the left out $u - v$ path in opposite direction. It is strongly connected and is called a Diglobe. It is denoted as $\overrightarrow{Gl}(n)$.

Figure 1.1 : Diglobe

Definition: If the edges of all $u - v$ paths are in a single common direction it is not a strong digraph. We name it as sole diglobe $\overrightarrow{SGL}(n)$.

Remark: If there are atleast two paths are oriented in opposite directions, the diglobe becomes strongly connected.

Remark: Orient the edges of the globe in such a way that the two edges in each $u - v$ path of length 2 get opposite directions. The resulting digraph is called alternate diglobe and is denoted as $\overrightarrow{AGL}(n)$. $\overrightarrow{AGL}(n)$ is not a strong digraph.

Definition: Consider a book with n pages sharing a common edge. The common edge is called the spine or base of the book. Orient all the edges except the spine in the one single direction and the spine in opposite direction. The resulting digraph is strongly connected and is called as directed book. The directed book is denoted as $\overrightarrow{B}(m, n)$.

Remark: The ditriangular book with n -pages is defined as n copies of cycle C_3 sharing a common edge in a directed book. The ditriangular book is denoted as $\overrightarrow{B}(3, n)$.

Figure 1.2: Ditriangular Book

Remark: The diquadrilateral book with n -pages is defined as n copies of cycle C_4 sharing a common edge in a directed book. The diquadrilateral book is denoted as $\overrightarrow{B}(4, n)$.

Figure 1.3: Diquadrilateral Book

II. MAIN RESULTS

Theorem 1: The radial radio mean square number of diglobe $(\overline{Gl(n)})$ is $n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Proof: Let D be a diglobe.

Let $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, u, v\}$ and

$$A(D) = \{\overline{uv_i} / 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor\} \cup \{\overline{uv_i} / \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 2 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{v_{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}u}\} \cup \{\overline{v_i v} / 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor\} \cup \{\overline{v_i v} / \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 2 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{vv_{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}\}$$

The radius of diglobe is 3.

Define $f: V(D) \rightarrow N$ by

$$f(v_i) = i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(u) = n + 1$$

$$f(v) = n + 2$$

Claim: f is a valid radial radio mean square labeling.

Since the radius is 3, to prove f is a radial radio mean labeling, it is enough to prove that,

$$\vec{d}(x, y) + \left\lceil \frac{(f(x))^2 + (f(y))^2}{2} \right\rceil \geq 4 \dots \dots \dots (1) \text{ for every pair of vertices } (x, y) \text{ where } x \neq y.$$

Equivalently, it is enough to prove (1) for pair of vertices with minimum f values and minimum

$\vec{d}(x, y)$ values. Hence, the proof involves the following cases

Case a: Consider the pairs (u, v_i) . Here, $\vec{d}(u, v_i) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(u, v_i) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(v_i)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{n + 1 + i}{2} \right\rceil \geq 4$$

Case b: Consider the pairs (v_i, v) . Here, $\vec{d}(v_i, v) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{i + n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 4$$

Case c: Consider the pairs (u, v) and $\vec{d}(u, v) = 2$

$$\vec{d}(u, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 2 + \left\lceil \frac{n + 1 + n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 4$$

Case d: Consider the pairs (v_i, v_{i+1}) and $\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 2$, then,

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v_{i+1})}{2} \right\rceil \geq 2 + \left\lceil \frac{i + i + 1}{2} \right\rceil > 4$$

Hence, by all the above cases, the radial radio mean square condition is satisfied by f .

Further, f attains its maximum corresponding to v and is $n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Since D contains only $n + 2$ vertices, $n + 2$ is the minimum of the maximum integer that could be assigned to the vertices of D under any radial radio mean square labeling.

Hence $rrmsn(D) = n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Theorem 2: The radial radio mean square number of ditriangular book $(\overline{B(3, n)})$ is $n + 2$ for $n > 1$.

Proof: Let D be a ditriangular book.

Let $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, u, v\}$ and

$$A(D) = \{\overrightarrow{uv_i}/1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overrightarrow{v_i v}/1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overrightarrow{vu}\}$$

The radius of ditriangular book is 2.

Define $f: V(D) \rightarrow N$ by

$$f(v_i) = i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(u) = n + 1$$

$$f(v) = n + 2$$

Claim: f is a valid radial radio mean square labeling.

Since the radius is 2, to prove f is a radial radio mean labeling, it is enough to prove that, $(x, y) + \overrightarrow{d}(x, y) + \left\lceil \frac{(f(x))^2 + (f(y))^2}{2} \right\rceil \geq 3 \dots \dots \dots (1)$ for every pair of vertices (x, y) where $x \neq y$.

Equivalently, it is enough to prove (1) for pair of vertices with minimum f values and minimum $\overrightarrow{d}(x, y)$ values. Hence, the proof involves the following cases

Case a: Consider the pairs (u, v_i) . Here, $\overrightarrow{d}(u, v_i) \geq 1$

$$\overrightarrow{d}(u, v_i) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(v_i)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{n + 1 + i}{2} \right\rceil > 3$$

Case b: Consider the pairs (v_i, v) . Here, $\overrightarrow{d}(v_i, v) \geq 1$

$$\overrightarrow{d}(v_i, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{i + n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 3$$

Case c: Consider the pairs (u, v) and $\overrightarrow{d}(u, v) = 1$

$$\overrightarrow{d}(u, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{n + 1 + n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 3$$

Case d: Consider the pairs (v_i, v_{i+1}) and $\overrightarrow{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 3$, then,

$$\overrightarrow{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v_{i+1})}{2} \right\rceil \geq 3 + \left\lceil \frac{i + i + 1}{2} \right\rceil > 3$$

Hence, by all the above cases, the radial radio mean square condition is satisfied by f .

Further, f attains its maximum corresponding to v and is $n + 2$ for $n > 1$.

Since D contains only $n + 2$ vertices, $n + 2$ is the minimum of the maximum integer that could be assigned to the vertices of D under any radial radio mean square labeling.

Hence $rrmsn(D) = n + 2$ for $n > 1$.

Theorem 3: The radial radio mean square number of diquadrilateral book $(\overrightarrow{B(4, n)})$ is $2n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Proof: Let D be a diquadrilateral book.

Let $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n, u, v\}$ and

$$A(D) = \{\overrightarrow{uu_i}/1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overrightarrow{u_i v_i}/1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overrightarrow{v_i v}/1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overrightarrow{vu}\}$$

The radius of diquadrilateral book is 4.

Define $f: V(D) \rightarrow N$ by

$$f(u_i) = i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_i) = n + i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(u) = 2n + 1$$

$$f(v) = 2n + 2$$

Claim: f is a valid radial radio mean square labeling.

Since the radius is 4, to prove f is a radial radio mean labeling, it is enough to prove that, $\vec{d}(x, y) + \left\lceil \frac{(f(x))^2 + (f(y))^2}{2} \right\rceil \geq 5 \dots \dots \dots (1)$ for every pair of vertices (x, y) where $x \neq y$.

Equivalently, it is enough to prove (1) for pair of vertices with minimum f values and minimum $\vec{d}(x, y)$ values. Hence, the proof involves the following cases

Case a: Consider the pairs (u, u_i) . Here, $\vec{d}(u, u_i) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(u, u_i) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(u_i)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{2n + 1 + i}{2} \right\rceil > 5$$

Case b: Consider the pairs (v_i, v) . Here, $\vec{d}(v_i, v) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{n + i + 2n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 5$$

Case c: Consider the pairs (u_i, v_i) and $\vec{d}(u_i, v_i) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(u_i, v_i) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u_i) + f(v_i)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{i + n + i}{2} \right\rceil \geq 5$$

Case d: Consider the pairs (u_i, u_{i+1}) and $\vec{d}(u_i, u_{i+1}) = 4$, then,

$$\vec{d}(u_i, u_{i+1}) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u_i) + f(u_{i+1})}{2} \right\rceil \geq 4 + \left\lceil \frac{i + i + 1}{2} \right\rceil > 5$$

Case e: Consider the pairs (v_i, v_{i+1}) and $\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 4$, then,

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v_{i+1})}{2} \right\rceil \geq 4 + \left\lceil \frac{n + i + n + i + 1}{2} \right\rceil > 5$$

Hence, by all the above cases, the radial radio mean square condition is satisfied by f .

Further, f attains its maximum corresponding to v and is $2n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Since D contains only $2n + 2$ vertices, $2n + 2$ is the minimum of the maximum integer that could be assigned to the vertices of D under any radial radio mean square labeling.

Hence, $rrmsn(D) = 2n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Theorem 4: The radial radio cube square difference number of diglobe $(\overline{Gl}(n))$ is $n + 1$ for $n > 2$.

Proof: Let D be a diglobe.

Let $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, u, v\}$ and

$$A(D) = \{\overline{uv_i} / 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor\} \cup \{\overline{uv_i} / \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 2 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{v_{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}u}\} \cup \{\overline{v_i v} / 1 \leq i \leq \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor\} \cup \{\overline{v_i v} / \lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 2 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{vv_{\lfloor \frac{n}{2} \rfloor + 1}}\}$$

The radius of diglobe is 3.

Define $f: V(D) \rightarrow N$ by

$$f(v_i) = i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(u) = n + 1$$

$$f(v) = n + 2$$

Claim: f is a valid radial radio cube square difference labeling.

Since the radius is 3, to prove f is a radial radio cube square difference labeling, it is enough to prove that,

$$\vec{d}(x, y) + [f(x) + f(y)]^3 - [f(x) - f(y)]^2 \geq 4 \dots \dots \dots (1) \text{ for every pair of vertices } (x, y) \text{ where } x \neq y.$$

Equivalently, it is enough to prove (1) for pair of vertices with minimum f values and minimum $\vec{d}(x, y)$ values. Hence, the proof involves the following cases

Case a: Consider the pairs (u, v_i) . Here, $\vec{d}(u, v_i) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(u, v_i) + \left\lfloor \frac{f(u) + f(v_i)}{2} \right\rfloor \geq 1 + \left\lfloor \frac{n+1+i}{2} \right\rfloor > 4$$

Case b: Consider the pairs (v_i, v) . Here, $\vec{d}(v_i, v) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v) + \left\lfloor \frac{f(v_i) + f(v)}{2} \right\rfloor \geq 1 + \left\lfloor \frac{i+n+2}{2} \right\rfloor > 4$$

Case c: Consider the pairs (u, v) and $\vec{d}(u, v) = 2$

$$\vec{d}(u, v) + \left\lfloor \frac{f(u) + f(v)}{2} \right\rfloor \geq 2 + \left\lfloor \frac{n+1+n+2}{2} \right\rfloor > 4$$

Case d: Consider the pairs (v_i, v_{i+1}) and $\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 2$, then,

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \left\lfloor \frac{f(v_i) + f(v_{i+1})}{2} \right\rfloor \geq 2 + \left\lfloor \frac{i+i+1}{2} \right\rfloor > 4$$

Hence, by all the above cases, the radial radio cube square difference condition is satisfied by f .

Further, f attains its maximum corresponding to v and is $n+2$ for $n > 2$.

Since D contains only $n+2$ vertices, $n+2$ is the minimum of the maximum integer that could be assigned to the vertices of D under any radial radio cube square difference labeling.

Hence $rrcsdn(D) = n+2$ for $n > 2$.

Theorem 5: The radial radio cube square difference number of ditriangular book $(\overline{B(3, n)})$ is $n+2$ for $n > 1$.

Proof: Let D be a ditriangular book.

Let $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, u, v\}$ and

$A(D) = \{\overline{uv_i} / 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{v_i v} / 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{vu}\}$

The radius of ditriangular book is 2.

Define $f: V(D) \rightarrow N$ by

$$f(v_i) = i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(u) = n+1$$

$$f(v) = n+2$$

Claim: f is a valid radial radio cube square difference labeling.

Since the radius is 2, to prove f is a radial radio cube square difference labeling, it is enough to prove that, $\vec{d}(x, y) + \left[[f(x) + f(y)]^3 - [f(x) - f(y)]^2 \right] \geq 3 \dots \dots \dots (1)$ for every pair of vertices (x, y) where $x \neq y$.

Equivalently, it is enough to prove (1) for pair of vertices with minimum f values and minimum $\vec{d}(x, y)$ values. Hence, the proof involves the following cases

Case a: Consider the pairs (u, v_i) . Here, $\vec{d}(u, v_i) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(u, v_i) + \left\lfloor \frac{f(u) + f(v_i)}{2} \right\rfloor \geq 1 + \left\lfloor \frac{n+1+i}{2} \right\rfloor > 3$$

Case b: Consider the pairs (v_i, v) . Here, $\vec{d}(v_i, v) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{i + n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 3$$

Case c: Consider the pairs (u, v) and $\vec{d}(u, v) = 1$

$$\vec{d}(u, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{n + 1 + n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 3$$

Case d: Consider the pairs (v_i, v_{i+1}) and $\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 3$, then,

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v_{i+1})}{2} \right\rceil \geq 3 + \left\lceil \frac{i + i + 1}{2} \right\rceil > 3$$

Hence, by all the above cases, the radial radio mean square condition is satisfied by f .

Further, f attains its maximum corresponding to v and is $n + 2$ for $n > 1$.

Since D contains only $n + 2$ vertices, $n + 2$ is the minimum of the maximum integer that could be assigned to the vertices of D under any radial radio cube square difference labeling.

Hence $rrcsdn(D) = n + 2$ for $n > 1$.

Theorem 6: The radial radio cube difference number of diquadrilateral book $(\overline{B(4, n)})$ is $2n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Proof: Let D be a diquadrilateral book.

Let $V(D) = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n, u_1, u_2, u_3, \dots, u_n, u, v\}$ and

$A(D) = \{\overline{uu_i} / 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{u_i v_i} / 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{v_i v} / 1 \leq i \leq n\} \cup \{\overline{vu}\}$

The radius of diquadrilateral book is 4.

Define $f: V(D) \rightarrow N$ by

$$f(u_i) = i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n$$

$$f(v_i) = n + i, \quad 1 \leq i \leq n - 1$$

$$f(u) = 2n + 1$$

$$f(v) = 2n + 2$$

Claim: f is a valid radial radio cube square difference labeling.

Since the radius is 4, to prove f is a radial radio cube square difference labeling, it is enough to prove that, $\vec{d}(x, y) + [f(x) + f(y)]^3 - [f(x) - f(y)]^2 \geq 5 \dots \dots \dots (1)$ for every pair of vertices (x, y) where $x \neq y$.

Equivalently, it is enough to prove (1) for pair of vertices with minimum f values and minimum $\vec{d}(x, y)$ values. Hence, the proof involves the following cases

Case a: Consider the pairs (u, u_i) . Here, $\vec{d}(u, u_i) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(u, u_i) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u) + f(u_i)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{2n + i + 1}{2} \right\rceil > 5$$

Case b: Consider the pairs (v_i, v) . Here, $\vec{d}(v_i, v) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v) + \left\lceil \frac{f(v_i) + f(v)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{n + i + 2n + 2}{2} \right\rceil > 5$$

Case c: Consider the pairs (u_i, v_i) and $\vec{d}(u_i, v_i) \geq 1$

$$\vec{d}(u_i, v_i) + \left\lceil \frac{f(u_i) + f(v_i)}{2} \right\rceil \geq 1 + \left\lceil \frac{i + n + i}{2} \right\rceil \geq 5$$

Case d: Consider the pairs (u_i, u_{i+1}) and $\vec{d}(u_i, u_{i+1}) = 4$, then,

$$\vec{d}(u_i, u_{i+1}) + \left\lfloor \frac{f(u_i) + f(u_{i+1})}{2} \right\rfloor \geq 4 + \left\lfloor \frac{i + i + 1}{2} \right\rfloor > 5$$

Case e: Consider the pairs (v_i, v_{i+1}) and $\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) = 4$, then,

$$\vec{d}(v_i, v_{i+1}) + \left\lfloor \frac{f(v_i) + f(v_{i+1})}{2} \right\rfloor \geq 4 + \left\lfloor \frac{n + i + n + i + 1}{2} \right\rfloor > 5$$

Hence, by all the above cases, the radial radio cube square difference condition is satisfied by f .

Further, f attains its maximum corresponding to v and is $2n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

Since D contains only $2n + 2$ vertices, $2n + 2$ is the minimum of the maximum integer that could be assigned to the vertices of D under any radial radio cube square difference labeling.

Hence, $rrcsdn(D) = 2n + 2$ for $n > 2$.

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